

Initial Results from an Open-Source Workflow for Streamlined Nuclear Data Sensitivity and Uncertainty Analysis

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ABSTRACT

This work presents preliminary results from a novel, fully-open source workflow that combines the codes SANDY and FRENDY to streamline nuclear data uncertainty propagation through eigenvalue calculations in OpenMC. This workflow makes use of both the direct perturbation and random sampling methodologies to perform uncertainty quantification of k_{eff} values and point kinetics parameters. The criticality experiment Jezebel was utilized as a benchmark for the workflow, and initial benchmarking results showed general agreement with work previously conducted. Good agreement was shown for the uncertainty of k_{eff} between the workflow's methodologies for Jezebel with results being within 30 pcm, confirming the correct implementation of the methods in the workflow. The workflow was then applied to the Kilopower Reactor Using Stirling Technology (KRUSTY) design with the effects of the Be-9 elastic scattering and the U-235 fission cross sections being examined. Even for KRUSTY, the uncertainty on k_{eff} computed from the direct perturbation and random sampling agreed within 8 pcm, further confirming the correctness of the workflow. Future work directions include release of the workflow into a public GitHub repository, examining the effects of other nuclear data such as $\bar{\nu}$, examining the uncertainty caused by nuclear data near 0 K, and coupling the workflow with thermal solvers to propagate uncertainty through multiphysics eigenvalue calculations.

Keywords: uncertainty quantification, sensitivity analysis, Jezebel, KRUSTY

1. INTRODUCTION

The proper quantification of uncertainty is key in correctly predicting the behavior of nuclear reactors. While the numerical error from Monte Carlo (MC) calculations is usually accounted for in eigenvalue calculations, there are other sources of uncertainty that are frequently overlooked or neglected in reactor modeling. One such source of error is the uncertainty present in continuous-energy nuclear data. Being able to account for and quantify the effects of this uncertainty source allows engineers to gain a greater insight into the accuracy of their models. Additionally, proper computation of uncertainties can help identify gaps in cross sections' knowledge, and it can be used to direct future research for the purpose of reducing the sources of error. This is especially true for elements like Be which aren't used in conventional LWRs and thus haven't been researched as much as other elements like Zr or U, but are being investigated as materials of choice for advanced reactor designs [1, 2].

The two main codes to perform uncertainty propagation in eigenvalue calculations, TSUNAMI and Whisper, are export-controlled codes [3, 4]. Other codes that are open-source, such as TOFFEE, either have been developed to leverage the output of export-controlled codes (e.g., MCNP), or they have limitations in their workflow [5]. For example, the open-source code FRENDY has the ability to perform random sampling of cross sections using covariance data, but needs to have external covariance data files be input by the user [6]. Additionally, the open-source code SANDY can be used to create perturbed files using random sampling, but it is unable to produce directly perturbed cross section files due to PENDF perturbations being altered during ACE file exportation [7].

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In this work, we present a novel open-source workflow that combines SANDY and FRENDY to perform nuclear data sensitivity analysis and uncertainty quantification in OpenMC eigenvalue calculations [7, 8, 9]. The workflow can be leveraged to perform both direct nuclear data perturbation for sensitivity analysis and random sampling-based uncertainty quantification. Covariance matrices are used to propagate uncertainty to the outputs through the use of bi-linear products with the sensitivity coefficients' vector [7]. We think that this fully-open source workflow will streamline uncertainty propagation calculations with OpenMC while complementing ongoing work aimed at implementing adjoint-weighted sensitivity coefficients in OpenMC. In particular, it will provide a streamlined way to perform verification of results obtained through the generalized perturbation theory [10].

We benchmark this workflow with a model of the Jezebel criticality experiment, and apply the workflow to a model of the Kilowatt Reactor Using Stirling Technology (KRUSTY) [2]. For both models, the uncertainty propagation obtained using the direct perturbation approach is compared with that derived from random sampling. The two methods show good agreement, thereby confirming the consistency of the direct perturbation method with the random sampling implementation.

The structure of this paper is as follows. Section 2 covers essential concepts related to the sensitivity analysis and uncertainty quantification methods, and summarizes the created workflow. Section 3 covers initial results of the workflow's benchmarking with the Jezebel experiment, and presents initial results of the workflow being applied to KRUSTY. Section 4 provides conclusions, including a summary of the work conducted and planned future work directions.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Sensitivity Analysis and Uncertainty Quantification Overview

Sensitivity analysis in the context of nuclear reactor simulations is the process of examining how one or more outputs of a simulation change due to perturbations to one or more inputs. For this work, microscopic cross sections served as the input parameters of interest, and k_{eff} values and Point Kinetics Equations (PKE) parameters served as the output parameters of investigation. Sensitivity coefficients are a means by which the changes in output parameters due to changes to input parameters can be quantified. The formula for a relative sensitivity coefficient ($S_{y,x}$) is given by:

$$S_{y,x} = \frac{x}{y} \frac{\partial y}{\partial x} \quad (1)$$

Where x is the input parameter and y is the output parameter. In this work, the partial derivative in Eq. 1 was approximated using a forward-differencing method under the assumption that changes to x are small enough that linearity between the input and output can be assumed. Additionally, absolute sensitivity coefficients were utilized which are similar to relative versions, except that they don't include the multiplication by x/y . Absolute sensitivity coefficients can be used to compute the variance on outputs due to the uncertainty in the cross section data using the Sandwich Rule where the variance of the output, denoted by δ_y^2 , is given by:

$$\delta_y^2 = \mathbf{S} \cdot \mathbf{COV} \cdot \mathbf{S}^T \quad (2)$$

Where \mathbf{S} is a vector of absolute sensitivity coefficients calculated for cross section perturbations, \mathbf{COV} is the absolute covariance matrix for the cross section being perturbed, and \mathbf{S}^T is the transpose \mathbf{S} [11]. For the calculation of the sensitivity coefficients, the direct perturbation method was utilized, where the cross section values within an energy interval of interest were multiplied by a constant. Following the perturbation, redundant cross sections were reconstructed based on correlations. Since perturbations

are applied over an energy interval, the value of the cross section at the midpoint energy of the interval is used to calculate the corresponding sensitivity coefficient in the forward-differencing method.

Another method of calculating the uncertainty of the output due to the uncertainty of some cross section of interest is via the random sampling method [11]. In this method, the relative covariance matrix of the cross section data is used to randomly sample the cross sections and create perturbation coefficients that can then be applied to the cross section across a predetermined energy grid. Numerous sets of these perturbed cross sections are then used to run the model, and the variance of the output due to the cross section's uncertainty is then approximated using the variance of the perturbed output samples [11].

2.2. Workflow Overview

To conduct the sensitivity analysis and uncertainty quantification, a workflow was developed that made use of three open-source codes: SANDY, FRENDY, and OpenMC [7, 8, 9]. SANDY is a Python package originally developed to perform uncertainty propagation based on the random sampling of nuclear data [7]. Within this workflow, it serves as a means of retrieving the absolute and relative covariance matrices for the nuclide and reaction(s) of interest. FRENDY is a code developed by researchers within the Japan Atomic Energy Agency (JAEA) to generate and modify nuclear data in the form of ACE files [8]. FRENDY was utilized in this workflow to create ACE files from ENDF-formatted cross section data, generate randomly sampled perturbation coefficients, and to apply perturbations to the ACE-formatted cross section data to create perturbed ACE files. OpenMC is an open-source MC particle transport code, and it was the code utilized to perform the simulations using the perturbed ACE cross section files [9]. Post-processing of the results produced by OpenMC was conducted using Python scripts created by the authors. A diagram summarizing the workflow is shown in Figure 1.

3. NUMERICAL RESULTS

3.1. Jezebel Benchmarking

To benchmark the workflow methodology, calculations were conducted with an OpenMC model of the Jezebel experiment. The model was created based on Jezebel modeling information publicly available on GitHub[12]. The SCALE44 energy grid was used to define the perturbation intervals for the cross section data and the covariance matrices. This was done to have a fine enough grid to see general trends, but not too fine to cause issues with the ACE file creation. This is because FRENDY doesn't automatically add more tabulated cross section values to ensure that perturbations within fine energy grids can be performed properly [6]. For example, if the energy grid is fine enough that only one tabulated value falls within it, FRENDY is unable to perform the perturbation properly. As such, SCALE44 was chosen to allow for some level of detail without causing issues with perturbations not being performed correctly. Modifying FRENDY to remediate this issue is currently under investigation.

The random sampling was performed using 400 perturbed files and runs per analysis. This file number was chosen based on error analysis where 100 runs were performed during initial testing of the workflow's capabilities, and then the amount of files was quadrupled to reduce error by a factor of 2. Cross section data from the ENDF-B-VIII.0 evaluation was utilized for the simulations [13]. Each simulation of Jezebel was run using 2000 total batches, 25 inactive batches, and 1 million particles per batch to obtain a standard deviation of 1 pcm. The temperature of the model was set constant at 294 K.

The equivalent MCNP model was run to provide additional results verification. The same batch and particle statistics as the OpenMC Jezebel model were utilized with ENDF-B-VIII.0 cross section data at 293.6 K being utilized [13]. This was done to enable a comparison between the uncertainties obtained using the workflow and uncertainties obtained by combining sensitivity data calculated using MCNP's adjoint capabilities with covariance data [14].

A plot showing the relative sensitivity per lethargy width of k_{eff} to the Pu-239 fission cross section

Figure 1. Diagram outlining the steps in the workflow for the direct perturbation and random sampling methodologies for sensitivity analysis and uncertainty quantification.

found using the workflow is given as a function of energy in Figure 2. The overall shape of the curve in

Figure 2. Relative sensitivity per lethargy width of the Pu-239 fission cross section as a function of energy within Jezebel. The energy bounds were truncated to enable better comparison with results in the literature [15].

Figure 2 closely follows results found in literature for the sensitivity found with adjoint-based methods using MCNP, providing confidence in the validity of the sensitivity analysis results [15].

A summary of the uncertainty on k_{eff} found using the direct perturbation, random sampling, and MCNP adjoint methods for several Pu-239 cross sections is given in Table I. The results from the workflow were found to be in general agreement with the uncertainty quantification results from previous work for Jezebel that utilized MCNP with the ENDF-B-VIII.0 library [5]. Good agreement was also shown between the workflow's results and those obtained using the MCNP model. The maximum difference between methods was approximately 27 pcm between the random sampling and MCNP adjoint methods. This supports that the workflow can find results comparable to those obtained with adjoint capabilities. The uncertainty found between the direct perturbation and random sampling methods was found to be in good agreement as well. The maximum difference in uncertainty was approximately 30 pcm between the two methods, confirming the correct implementation of the methods in the workflow.

Table I. Summary of the uncertainty on k_{eff} found for the Jezebel model due to several Pu-239 cross sections.

Nuclide(Cross Section)	Direct Perturbation	Random Sampling	MCNP Adjoint
Pu-239 (n, fission)	891 pcm	886 pcm	909 pcm
Pu-239 (n, inelastic)	841 pcm	871 pcm	856 pcm
Pu-239 (n, elastic)	484 pcm	464 pcm	491 pcm
Pu-239 (n, radiative capture)	81 pcm	70 pcm	77 pcm

3.2. KRUSTY Testing

The KRUSTY reactor was a test nuclear reactor developed by NASA and the U.S. Department of Energy (DOE) to demonstrate compact fission power systems for space missions [2]. Radial and axial cross sectional views of the geometry produced with OpenMC for the KRUSTY model are shown in Figure 3. Critical Configuration 1 from the ICSBEP handbook document was chosen for modeling due to it being used for sensitivity analysis in previous work [16]. The reported k_{eff} for modeling of the configuration is 1.00028 ± 0.00001 [17]. The average k_{eff} of the OpenMC model was 1.00029 ± 0.00002 across three runs with different random seeds. The excellent agreement between the k_{eff} results verifies that the OpenMC model is a suitable representation for the modeling within the handbook.

Same as for the Jezebel benchmarking, the SCALE44 energy grid was utilized to determine the energy bins for the cross section covariances and the perturbation intervals. Each uncertainty quantification analysis of KRUSTY utilized 400 randomly sampled cross section files and simulations for the same reasons as mentioned prior for Jezebel. The temperature of materials in the simulations was set constant at 294 K, and all simulations were ran with 1200 total batches, 50 inactive batches, and 1 million particles per batch.

Plots of the relative sensitivity per lethargy width for the Be-9 elastic scattering and U-235 fission cross sections versus incident neutron energy are given in Figs.4a–4b respectively. From the plots, it can be seen that the k_{eff} value for the KRUSTY model is more sensitive to both of the cross sections at higher neutron energies, which is reasonable given that KRUSTY was designed to have a fast neutron spectrum [2].

A summary of the uncertainties on k_{eff} due to the uncertainties of the cross section data for Be-9 elastic scattering and U-235 fission is given in Table II. It can be seen that the uncertainty on k_{eff} for KRUSTY due to the U-235 fission cross section was approximately a factor of 4 greater than that caused by the Be-9 elastic scattering cross section. Additionally, the uncertainties on k_{eff} found between the direct perturbation and random sampling methods for each cross section showed good agreement with each other as their results were within 8 pcm.

To further verify the workflow's capabilities, we evaluated the uncertainties in the Λ_{eff} and Rossi- α

Figure 3. Radial and axial cross-sectional views of the KRUSTY model geometry. The colors and their corresponding materials are: orange, fuel material; blue, BeO reflector material; lime, 304SS; green, 316SS; red, Al; purple, B₄C absorber material; black, AmBe source material; and pink, 4140 steel.

Figure 4. k_{eff} relative sensitivity per lethargy width for two cross sections within KRUSTY.

Table II. Summary of the uncertainties on k_{eff} found for the KRUSTY model.

Nuclide(Cross Section)	Direct Perturbation Uncertainty	Random Sampling Uncertainty
Be-9 (n, elastic)	156 pcm	163 pcm
U-235 (n, fission)	616 pcm	608 pcm

parameters, summarized in Table III [18]. Simulations used 1,200 total batches, 50 inactive batches, 10 million particles per batch, and 5 IFP generations to reduce statistical noise. Due to the computational expense needed to lower the variance of the IFP-computed PKE parameters, stochastic-sampling results are not reported. For both parameters, uncertainties were dominated by the U-235 fission cross section rather than the Be-9 elastic-scattering cross section. Results for β_{eff} were also generated but are omitted pending further investigation into significant stochastic-noise effects. Sensitivity profiles for α as a function of energy are provided in Fig. 5 for completeness. Based on Tables II–III, U-235’s fission cross

section has a greater effect on the uncertainty of the effective multiplication factor and PK parameters compared to Be-9's elastic scattering cross section.

Figure 5. Rossi- α relative sensitivity per lethargy width for two cross sections within KRUSTY.

Table III. Summary of the uncertainties for some PKE parameters found for the KRUSTY model.

PKE Parameter	MC σ	Be-9 (n,elastic)	U-235 (n,fission)
Λ_{eff} [μs]	0.00117	0.05486	0.08597
Rossi- α [μs^{-1}]	5.8496×10^{-7}	1.2171×10^{-5}	2.2104×10^{-5}

4. CONCLUSIONS

A workflow consisting of open-source codes designed to streamline sensitivity analysis and uncertainty quantification using nuclear cross section data was created. This workflow was benchmarked through its application to a model of Jezebel with results from the benchmark being in general agreement with previous work. Additionally, results for the KRUSTY reactor were obtained, with the Be-9 elastic scattering and the U-235 fission cross sections being examined in detail within this work. The uncertainty on k_{eff} found using both the direct perturbation and random sampling methods with KRUSTY were in agreement within 8 pcm for their respective cross section. Initial results for the uncertainty of some PKE parameters, specifically Λ_{eff} and Rossi- α , for KRUSTY were also obtained for KRUSTY, indicating that uncertainties in the U-235 fission cross section dominate over those from Be scattering. While this result is specific to KRUSTY, the relative contributions may differ in thermal systems, motivating additional test cases to assess whether reevaluation of Be cross-section data is warranted for criticality analyses.

In future work, we intend to tighten this workflow to be included in a public GitHub repository. Additionally, we will extend the workflow to work with other nuclear data, such as the average number of neutrons produced per fission ($\bar{\nu}$) to investigate the sensitivities and uncertainties due to other parameters. Further verification to test the workflow for thermal systems will be performed for an upcoming journal publication. Finally, we plan to pursue extending this workflow to study uncertainty through multiphysics problems obtained by coupling OpenMC with thermal solvers.

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